

An Emerging Trend in Governance of Non-Performing Assets

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Abstract

The Indian banking system is plagued with non-performing assets (NPAs). Non-Performing Asset (NPA) is a loan that is in jeopardy of avoidance. Banks in their account books enter loans and advances as assets which add interest income to the banks. Any reduction in these assets affects the liquidity income of banks and accordingly the profitability. As the NPAs disturb the lending capacity of banks, it affects the potential unaffected borrowers. NPAs are the main reason for draining and flagging the financial strength of the Banks. NPA despairs may continue for banks in 2018-19 due to current economic situation: RBI.

The prompt identification and accurate measurement of non-performing assets (NPAs) provide self-assurance to market participants and supervisors in banks' reported asset quality metrics, earnings performance and regulatory capital ratios - all of which are critical to fostering financial stability. To increase the profitability and efficiency of banks, the NPAs are strictly reduced and measured. Hence, Quality of the asset specifies how much of the loans taken by the borrowers are refunded in the form of interests and principal amount for 90 days.

Keywords: Governance, NPA, Issues, Risks.

Introduction

Growing non-performing assets is a recurring problem in the Indian banking sector. Over the past two decades, there have been two such episodes when the banking sector was severely reduced by balance sheet problem. The banking system is the heart of the financial system. The major purpose of the financial system is the utilization of the public savings and its allocation in different sectors of the economy as an investment. The conversion of financial savings into investment is known as the procedure of capital formation in the budget. How this process of financial intermediation (i.e. collecting scattered savings and using it in to productive purposive) is carried out shall imitate the efficiency of the financial institutions and their role in socio-economic transformation of the nation.

Banks are considered to be mirrors of health of an economy and are a pre-requisite for the overall solidity and financial development of the economy. Escalating non-performing assets, especially of state-owned banks, weaken the stability of such entities and have thus become a main anxiety for the Indian financial system. In addition to

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 affecting the strength of a bank, NPAs imitate a distress in the economy. They destruct the whole credit distribution structure and even lead to main financial disturbances.

Banking Environment in India

Types of NPA’s

Banks are required to categorize NPAs further into Substandard, Doubtful and Loss assets:-

- Substandard Assets: An assets which has endured NPA for a period less than or equal to 12months.
- Doubtful Assets: An asset would be confidential as insecure if it has remained in the substandard category for a period of 12months.
- Loss Assets: As per RBI, “Loss asset is considered uncollectible and of such little assessment that its endurance as a bankable asset is not warranted, although there may be some salvage or recovery value.”

Governance Issue

- Change of funds by companies for resolutions other than for which loans were taken.
- Due to attentiveness not done in early payment of loans.
- Inefficiencies in post payment monitoring of the problem.
- Reformation of loans done by banks earlier to avoid provisioning. Post restriction by RBI, banks are required to clear their asset books which has led to sudden spout in NPAs
- During the time of financial boom, overconfidence shown by corporate was taken on face value by banks and adequate background check was not done in proceeding loan
- In the lack of adequate governance mechanism, double leveraging by corporate, as pointed out by RBI’s Financial Stability Report.

Why did the existing schemes fail?

The NPA story is not inventive in India and several steps have been taken by the government on legal, financial and policy level reforms. Taking note of the existing anxious assets and NPA situation, the RBI introduced a host of schemes and outlines with the aim of curtailing the growing NPAs.

1. Joint Lenders’ Forum and plan (January 2014)

Banks would need to constitute a committee called JLF and roll out a CAP comprising rectification, restructuring and recovery of loans.

2. Strategic Debt Restructuring (SDR) (June 2015)

This was presented with the aim of helping banks to recover their loans by taking control of distressed listed companies.

3. Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code (May 2016)

This is the sturdiest measure taken so far, yet due to lack of operational guidelines and a legal framework, the code too has its fair portion of critics.

4. Scheme for Sustainable Structuring of Stressed Assets (S4A)- (June 2016)

RBI introduced (S4A) for the resolution of bad loans of large projects. This is meant at strengthening the lenders' ability to deal with stressed assets by providing an avenue for reworking the financial structure of entities facing unaffected complications.

Impacts of NPAs

The efficiency of a bank is not imitated only by the size of its balance sheet but also the level of return on its assets. The NPAs do not generate interest income for banks but at the same time banks are required to provide provisions for NPAs from their present profits.

- The complex is the amount of non-performing assets (NPA) the leaner will be the bank's revenue stream.
- Indian banking sector has been facing the NPA issue due to the mishandling in the loan distribution carried by the Public sector banks.
- As the NPAs of the banks will rise, it will bring a scarcity of funds in the Indian markets. Few banks will be eager to lend if they are not sure of the retrieval of their money.
- The stakeholders of the banks will lose of money as banks themselves will find it tough to live in the market.
- This will lead to a disaster situation in the market.
- The price of loans, interest rates will shoot up badly. Shooting of interest rates will directly influence the investors who wish to take loans for setting up infrastructural, industrial projects etc.
- It will also influence the retail consumers, who will have to shell out a higher attention rate for a loan.
- All these issuesoffended the overall demand in the Indian economy.
- Finally, it will lead to lower growth and higher inflation because of the higher cost of capital.

Five ways government, RBI trying to speed up NPA recovery

1. Alteration in banking law to give RBI more powers.
2. Stringent NPA recovery rules.
3. RBI’s loan restructuring schemes.
4. Present NPA scenario.
5. Banks may need to take a “hair cut”.

What Next?

More than 70 per cent of these cases will be restructuring and resolutions wherein the debt will be written down to supportable levels. Banks will take impartiality positions in these companies and new investors will provide additional capital. These companies would be then run with higher governance oversight and stricter loan treaties. As banks will take debt haircuts, promoters will take significant impartiality haircuts and new investors will ensure better management of these companies going forward. Capital allocation and efficiency will be the key for these companies as they try to tread back the path to routine. We estimate that around Rs 40,000-50,000 crore of new additional capital will have to be filled to make these companies perform efficiently again. This will be filled by a mixture of present promoters, ARCs, stressed advantage funds and private equity (PE) investors. These investors will also drive the turnaround for these companies through stronger oversight.

Current developments on NPA

Worst of the NPA crisis is over, says RBI report.

According to the FSR, gross NPAs ratio declined to 10.8% in September 2018 from 11.5 % in March 2018. According to the Reserve of Bank of India (RBI), banks will continue to face decline in their non-performing assets (NPAs) or bad loans due to the current economic conditions in the current fiscal year. The gross non-performing assets (GNPAs) plus updated standard advances in the banking system remained elevated at 12.1 per cent of gross advances at end-March 2018, RBI’s annual report for 2017-18 stated.

“Going forward, the stress tests carried out by the Reserve Bank suggest that under the baseline assumption of the current financial situation usual, the GNPA ratio of scheduled commercial banks (SCBs) may increase further in 2018-19,” it said.

The aggregate gross NPAs of SCBs increased primarily as a result of this transparent credit of stressed assets as NPAs, from Rs 3,23,464 crore, as on March 31, 2015, to Rs 10,35,528 crore, as on March 31, 2018. In order to curb NPAs, RBI also put in place revised and harmonised guidelines for resolution of stressed assets during the year, exchanging earlier schemes.

- According to the Reserve Bank of India's latest "Financial Stability Report", Gross non-performing assets (NPAs) rose from 9.2% in September 2016 to 9.6% in March 2017.
- Stress tests lead by the RBI indicates that this number could rise to 10.2% under the baseline scenario.
- Return on assets is negative.
- The net non-performance advance (NNPA) ratio marginally increased to 5.5% in March 2017 from 5.4% in September 2016.
- The RBI in its Financial Stability Report (FSR) highlighted that stressed advances ratio declined from 12.3% to 12% due to fall in restructured standard advances.

The Reserve Bank of India today unrestricted the eighteenth issue of the Financial Stability Report (FSR). The FSR reflects the cooperative assessment of the Sub-Committee of the Financial Constancy and Development Council (FSDC) on risks to financial stability, as also the resilience of the financial system. The Report also discusses issues connecting to growth and guideline of the financial sector.

Overall assessment of systematic risks

India's financial system ruins stable, and the banking sector shows signs of growth, even though the global economic environment and the emerging trends in financial sector pose challenges.

Global and domestic macro-financial risks

- The global growth position for 2018 and 2019 remains steady even though the underlying downside risks have risen.
- Spill-over risk to emerging economies caused by tightening of financial conditions in Advanced Economies, protectionist trade policies and global geopolitical tension has significantly increased.
- The gradual financial policy normalization in advanced economies (AEs) as also the uncertainty in global trade regime may unfavorably affect capital streams to emerging markets (EMs) and exert upward pressure on EM interest rates and corporate spreads.
- On the domestic front, growth of gross domestic product (GDP) showed slight moderation in Q2:2018-2019 while rise remains contained.
- In domestic financial markets, structural shifts in credit intermediation and the developing interconnectivity between banks and the non-banks call for greater caution.

Financial Institutions: Performance and risks

- Credit growth of scheduled commercial banks (SCBs) has enhanced between March 2018 and September 2018, driven largely by private sector banks (PVBs).
- The asset quality of banks showed an improvement with the gross non-performing assets (GNPA) ratio of SCBs decreasing from 11.5 per cent in March 2018 to 10.8 per cent in September 2018.
- Under the baseline scenario, GNPA ratio may deterioration from 10.8 per cent in September 2018 to 10.3 per cent in March 2019.
- Analysis of the financial network structure for the period September 2017 – September 2018 reveals a dwindling inter-bank market and increasing bank linkages with asset management companies-mutual funds (AMC-MFs) for raising funds and with NBFCs/Housing Finance Companies (HFCs) for lending.

Advantages of New Scheme

- To help bring back credit flow to stressed sectors such as steel etc as credit advancing condition have been eased in the scheme
- Banks can rework their worried accounts under the lapse of an external agency. This means greater clearness in functioning of banks. This is a provision of the scheme itself. Banks had earlier complained of involvement by critical agencies in probing bad debt which made it difficult for them to go for restructuring in even genuine cases
- This scheme would not only reinforce the lenders’ ability to deal with stressed assets, but would also put real assets back on track, promoting both banks and the promoters of anxious entities.

Conclusion

Growing out of the problem appears to be the most efficient and quickest method to resolve a banking crisis. RBI as the banking regulator, government as a major stake-holder and the banks themselves must step up to guarantee that the current crisis is resolved rapidly and in future, the flow of the credit to the real sector is not disrupted so much so that public finances have to be involved to rescue the banks. This calls for building adequate controlling capacity, comprehensive reforms in bank regulation and supervision, a strong legal framework for resolution, and policy thinking on the merits of government ownership of banks.

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